
FEATURES OF INITIAL TRAINING OF YOUNG VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS

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Abstract. *In this article, it is stated that comprehensive training in initial and general basic training should be taken into account, developing the physical qualities of young athletes and having a positive effect on the growth of their sports results.*

Keywords: *initial training, pedagogical observation, athletes, young volleyball players, training.*

INTRODUCTION

Literature sources, pedagogical observations, and practical experience of experts show that the selection of children of primary training groups, selection and training of young volleyball players at the next stage is considered an important and responsible task, as well as preparation for the upcoming process.

It is necessary to prepare on the basis of a multi-year step-by-step plan, to revive the individual abilities of young athletes, to create conditions for the maximum manifestation of the body's reserve capabilities, which is considered an important factor in the selection of vital abilities in the next periods of multi-year preparation.

Thus, the interrelationship between selection and training allows for the gradual selection of athletes and the gradual development of their physical qualities, the acquisition and improvement of technical and tactical skills in the chosen sport .

The content of the initial period of training young volleyball players is of special importance. According to a number of experts, the content of training during the initial training period is necessary for the physical development of children, strengthening of the basic movement apparatus, training of physical qualities (speed, coordination skills, dexterity, etc.), including mastering the basics of volleyball technique. should consist of the use of tools that help to educate special physical qualities and abilities.

Many authors take into account the characteristics of the child's organism, the level of physical development readiness . It is recommended to use folk action games in the initial stages of training as a means of physical and sometimes technical training.

After each year of training, necessary adjustments are made to the training of young athletes, including adjustments to the distribution of the volume of exercise components and the focus of training during the annual period. Compared to the first academic year, in the second academic year, the number of hours of tactical and integral training will be increased due to the reduction of the time allocated to general physical training. During the second year of training, the issue of expanding the set of technical methods and tactical actions studied will also be resolved.

In training groups, the requirements are even higher, for example, the volume of hours per year reaches 520 hours here, which is 104 hours more than in primary training groups . In the distribution of training types, 25% is spent on technical training, 28% on tactical training, and 21% on integral training.

A number of specialists consider it necessary to use folk movement games as preparation for volleyball along with physical exercises to solve the initial issues of preparation. Because in the period of primary and general basic training, they help to solve the issues of physical development and to educate physical and psychological qualities and expand children's movement methods, which are very important for acquiring technical and tactical actions. However, we could not find in the literature special works dedicated to the study of the effectiveness of using folk dynamic games in the selection and training of young volleyball players.

In the general basic training, which is considered a logical continuation of the first stage, relatively more complex issues must be solved, which is why the content of the training is regularly becoming more complex. Taking into account the characteristics of the developing body, including the senate period of the child's body development, the means of preparation are reduced .

The contents of the training of young volleyball players include mini-handball and mini-basketball exercises according to simplified rules for the development of speed, agility and speed-strength qualities, preparation and orientation exercises for the development of special qualities and abilities that facilitate the acquisition of game techniques and technical movements, educational and control games are included.

A number of experts recommend to include possible gymnastic, acrobatic, athletics exercises, swimming exercises taking into account the age and physical abilities of the participants. During this period, great attention should be paid to the issues of game technique, mini-volleyball (12-year-old children), volleyball (18-14-year-old children) and, of course, the selection of children for special volleyball training.

In the period of primary training, the characteristics of the construction of training activities are the use of the principle of universality in the selection of tools and methods, a deep study of the characteristics of each activity .

The main direction of the lesson programs is teaching, the process of its implementation is to create conditions for successful training of young volleyball players in a wide range of technical techniques and to create the necessary foundations for achieving a high level of special physical fitness in the subsequent years of training depends.

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